

Synthesis of Some Enaminonitriles

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Several substituted cyanoacetamides were prepared which were converted into α -cyano- α , α -bis(β -cyanoethyl) (R) amides. A series of products obtained by cyanoethylation were subjected to Thorpe-Ziegler cyclization. The intermolecular condensation takes place and cyclic enaminonitriles are formed. They have been characterized by infrared and ultraviolet spectroscopy.

In an earlier communications, the cyanoethylation reaction has been successfully applied towards synthesizing insecticides, pressor active compounds and coordination compounds. It was worthwhile to study that such compounds can also undergo Thorpe-Ziegler cyclization. It is with this idea that several cyanoethylated cyanoacetanilides, substituted cyanoacetanilides, cyanoacetamides and malondibenzylamides have been synthesized and then cyclized by the route outlined below.

Pimelonitrile is readily cyclized with sodium hydride to 4-amino-2-cyanocyclohexene and substituted pimetonitriles react similarly¹. The Thorpe-Ziegler cyclization is equally applicable to the synthesis of spiro derivatives of 1-amino-2-cyanocyclohexane. Thus bis-cyanoethylation product of fluorene² is also cyclized.

Hammer and Hines³ have studied the Thorpe-Ziegler reaction in case of five membered ringe.

Experimental

Cyanoacet-methylamide : Ethylcyanoacetate (5 g, 0.044 mol), 25% methylamine solution (6.48 g, 0.044 mol) and 0.02 g of sodium hydroxide were taken in a round bottomed flask. The mixture was shaken to make it homogeneous. It was then heated on a water bath for two hours and cooled. The solid

mass thus separated, was recrystallized from benzene. The cyanoacetamides were characterized by their sharp melting points and analysis (Table 1).

α , α -bis(β -cyanoethyl) cyanoacet-methylamide : To a stirred solution of cyanoacetmethylamide (2g, 0.02 mol) dioxan and Triton B (1 g) was added acrylonitrile (2.1 g, 0.04 mol), dropwise. Stirring was continued for four hours. The solution was neutralized with dil. HCl. The solid mass was recrystallized from alcohol. The cyanoethylated cyanoacetamides were characterized by their sharp melting points and analysis (Table 2).

1-Amnio, 2, 4 dicyano, 4 methylacetamido cyclohexane : 2.5 g of sodium slurry in dimethyl sulphoxide was added to a mixture of α , α -bis(β -cyanoethyl) cyanoacetmethylamide (4g, 0.02 mol). It was then heated on oil bath at 90-100° for two hours. After neutralizing with dil. acetic acid. It was poured in ice water and then extracted with ethyl acetate. The solid mas was crystallized from alcohol. These acetamidocyclohexenes were characterised by their sharp melting points and analyses (Table 3).

Discussion of Experimental Results : The Thorpe-Ziegler cyclization carried on nitriles described in the experimental part, gave cyclic products in very good

TABLE—1 ALKYL AND ARYL SUBSTITUTED CYANOACETAMIDES.

Sl. no.	Compound	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	Yields %	Percentage of Nitrogen Found	Calcd.
1.	Cyanoacet-methylamide	C ₄ H ₈ N ₂ O	101	40.90	28.60	28.57
2.	Cyanoacet-ethylamide	C ₅ H ₈ N ₂ O	74	50.50	25.10	25.00
3.	Cyanoacet-propylamide	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	45-46	43.80	22.15	22.20
4.	Cyanoacet-isopropylamide	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	65	43.80	22.40	22.20
5.	Cyanoacet-n-butylamide	C ₇ H ₁₂ N ₂ O	73	64.50	20.21	20.00
6.	Cyanoacet-o-toluidide	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	125	75.40	15.98	16.09
7.	Cyanoacet-benzylamide	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	120	76.50	16.12	16.09
8.	Cyanoacet-naphthylamide	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	175	87.90	13.50	13.30
9.	Cyanoacet-naphthylamide	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O	174	76.90	13.36	13.33

TABLE—4 INFRARED SPECTRA OF SUBSTITUTED CYCLOHEXENE

Sl. no.	Compound	NH frequencies in cm^{-1}	$-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequency in cm^{-1}	$\text{C}=\text{C}$ frequencies in cm^{-1}
1.	Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4 acetanilido cyclohexene	3510,3450 1650	2190,2250	1620
2.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano-4-p-chloro acetanilido cyclohexene	3450,3200 1645	2191,2250	1580
3.	1, Amino, 2, 4 dicyano, 4, methyl-acetamido cyclohexene	3450,3175 1637	2200,2252	1592
4.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4 ethyl-acetamido cyclohexene	3435,3137 1650	2198,2250	1608
5.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4-o-toluido cyclohexene	3500,3401 1625	2200,2260	1580
6.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4-benzylamido cyclohexene	3435,3130 1650	2202,2258	1580
7.	1, Amino, 2 cyano, 4, 4 dibenzylamido cyclohexene	3450,3150 1650	2190	1585

TABLE—5 ULTRAVIOLET SPECTRA OF SUBSTITUTED CYCLOHEXENES IN METHANOL

Sl. no.	Name of compound	λ_{max}	λ_{max}
1.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4 acetanilido cyclohexene	260	14,572
2.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4-p-chloro acetanilido cyclohexene	262	18,576
3.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4-methyl-acetamido cyclohexene	264	13,000
4.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4, methyl-acetamido cyclohexene	265	14,000
5.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4-o-toluido cyclohexene	260	13,230
6.	1, Amino, 2, 4-dicyano, 4-benzylamido cyclohexene	260	10,990
7.	1, Amino, 2-cyano, 4, 4, di benzylamidocyclohexene	263	22,155

The values of the nitrile frequencies in Table 3 have been depressed by $17\text{-}38\text{ cm}^{-1}$ below the 2218 cm^{-1} and occurs usually at 2190 cm^{-1} responsible for further shift of the nitrile frequency. Baldwin⁴ proposed that this abnormal shift is due to increased interaction between the p-electrons on the nitrogen atom and the π electrons of the double bond and in turn with the π electrons of the nitrile group itself.

Further support for the enaminonitrile structure (II) is the appearance of two bands in the $>\text{NH}$ stretching region i.e. at $3510\text{-}1$ and 3450 cm^{-1} . This is compatible only with a primary amino group. If an amino group were present, only one band should appear in this region⁸. The olefinic linkage is observed at 1620 cm^{-1} .

Therefore this abnormally large shift must be due to same influence other than simple conjugation with α, β -double bond. It has been stated by Hammer and Hines⁷ that the amino group was presumably

The ultra violet spectra of all the compounds listed in Table 5 offer further evidence for the existence of an unusual conjugated nitrile group, since there is a major absorption at $263\text{-}265\ \mu$. The E_{max} is from 10,000 to 22,000 which is also very intense and is also due to the amino group which has a powerful effect on UV absorption of these conjugated nitrile groups⁵.

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